

CITIZEN SCIENCE CONTACT POINT
RESEARCH

Tool 18

How the Department of Research - Outreach & Communication can help you promote and publicize your project at VUB

Welcome to the Citizen Science Starter Kit.

This document is part of Module 4 “Getting started with citizen science” (phase 3 – launch) and provides an overview of the opportunities in science outreach and communication offered by the Department of Research Outreach & Communication (ROC) to promote and publicize your project.

If you have any further questions, please contact citizenscience@vub.be.

RESEARCH - OUTREACH & COMMUNICATION (ROC)

Already in 1986, VUB created a Science Outreach department to break down the walls of the university. It has always been a pillar in the VUB's philosophy to translate research to a broader audience, to inspire the public with science, and vice versa.

Today, we are very proud that we keep underlining and strengthening this ambition with our Department of Research Outreach & Communication, supported by the Rectorate and the vice rectorate of Research, as well as [the Flemish Government](#) that partly subsidizes science outreach at Flemish higher education institutions, and various external funders related to our projects.

Visit our web page on the VUB Research Sharepoint > https://vub.sharepoint.com/sites/PUB_RD_SO

RESEARCH COMMUNICATION

ROC hosts the Communication Team of VUB's vice rectorate of Research. Not only do they manage the **social media channels** of the vice rectorate (LinkedIn, Twitter) and ROC (Facebook, Instagram, Twitter), but they are also responsible for the **Research Sharepoint environment**. Additionally, they serve as your **liaison** to the university's central communication department (MARCOM).

The Research Communication Team can help you communicate about important steps or milestones in your research (project), interesting results or developments, a call to be spread internally or amongst a wider audience ... More specifically, we have expertise in creating content for social media to get up close and personal with your audience.

Want to learn more? Drop us a line! > research.communication@vub.be

SCIENCE OUTREACH PROJECTS

ROC is responsible for the management of several science outreach projects, both **VUB-specific** as well as **in collaboration** with other Flemish/Brussels universities, university colleges and science communication/outreach organisations. The team is happy to think about the best way to **integrate your project** into these activities, to reach a wider audience and/or to gather input and participation.

<p>DAG VAN DE WETENSCHAP ('Science Festival')</p> <p>In cooperation with several Brussels institutions, we organize the annual 'Wetenschapsfestival Brussel' on the last Sunday of November. Present your research to a broad audience on this special day!</p> <p>https://www.dagvandewetenschap.be/</p>	
<p>VUB KINDERUNIVERSITEIT ('Childrens' University')</p> <p>Create a workshop for kids and inspire the next generation of young researchers!</p> <p>https://vubkinderuniversiteit.be</p>	
<p>DE BRUSSELE WETENSCHAPSBOX ('Science Box')</p> <p>This free do-it-yourself box for families includes a handful of scientific activities that children from the age of 6 (with a little help from grown-ups), teenagers and adults can get started with. All members of the family can get familiar with different scientific disciplines in an accessible, playful and practical way.</p>	

Stay tuned for some **new project ideas** we're developing. Do you have an idea for a science outreach activity yourself? Do not hesitate to let us know, we are happy to have a brainstorm and see where we can help. We also support researchers wanting to apply for [I Love Science](#), [Nerdland Festival](#) ...

SCIENCE OUTREACH TRAINING

Do you want to develop and sharpen your skills in science outreach communication? ROC ensures training for researchers via VUB TEO LRN in close collaboration with other departments at VUB, which are all listed on our [Sharepoint page](#). The offer is constantly evolving and includes training in writing (from blog writing, over opinion pieces to policy briefs), presenting (pitch your research), creating workshops for young audiences, developing communication strategies, creating content for social media and engaging in citizen science*.

Together with the other Flemish universities, we are organising 'Let's Talk Science', a three-day event taking place annually, in early July, and that is all about communicative competencies: a great chance for you to plunge headfirst into the world of science communication. Attend the plenary session, follow workshops and take part in the side program. The full programme can be found [here](#).

We also organise training related to participation in our activities, events or competitions:

[Doctoral Derby](#)

‘How to write a popularizing research summary?’ by Sven De Boeck

‘How to pitch your research’ by The Floor is Yours

[VUB Kinderuniversiteit](#)

‘How to score with your workshop for kids’ by Fran Geys and Sammy Leurs

PROJECT SUPPORT IN SCIENCE OUTREACH AND COMMUNICATION

Starting from the academic year 2023-2024, ROC is developing and offering **different support packages** in outreach and communication. These will range from advice in proposal writing, over the development of a communication strategy and plan, to tailored training and support during the first project year, and last but not least the full-on involvement in the project. Depending on your choice, the package will be free (basic support) or corresponding/ascending in budget requirements.

This overview will be updated as soon as the packages are officially launched.

For more information, contact research.communication@vub.be

*** CITIZEN SCIENCE CONTACT POINT**

Last but not least, ROC also houses the Citizen Science Contact Point! The CSCP currently offers tools, resources and support concerning communication and motivational strategies in citizen science research projects, and will likely also develop (online) training on the matter. Contact us at citizenscience@vub.be to learn more, and browse the other chapters and tools in this Starter Kit to get started. (Module 3, chapter 1 and 2; and Module 4, Phase 2)